

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D4.2 Evaluation results from experiments in semi-controlled realistic installations

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ACRONYMS LIST

CHSK	Crop Health Sensor Kit
NCK	Nutrient-content Kit
FW	Fresh Weight
DW	Dry Weight
TEAC	Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity
24VHELED	24-volt high efficiency light emitting diode
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
HSD	Honestly Significant Difference
PFD	Photon Flux Density
LED	Light Emitting Diode
NCK	Nutrient Content Kit

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The activity *T4.2 Experimentation in controlled realistic installations*, had as an objective - *To carry out pilot trials and provide feedback for the refinement and calibration of the GOhydro platform*. In order to fulfill this objective USAMV Cluj built 2 GOhydro platforms, identical, to be able to do experiments in parallel, both in semi-controlled conditions and in operational conditions. The GOhydro platform was built considering the recommendations of *Deliverable 2.1 Multi-modal Sensor Kit Specifications and Requirements*. To achieve semi-controlled conditions, one of the platforms was included in the grow tent Eden Grow XL Growbox Growtent homegrowing with dimensions of 240 x 120 x 200 cm. USAMV performed the test with the GOhydro platform in semi-controlled conditions, with 2 species: basil (2 varieties: Germaline Basilic Bio and Basil Grand Vert) and lettuce (3 varieties: Paris White, Little Gem and Lolla Rossa). The methodology used for the research was derived from deliverable *D4.1: Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units*. The growing conditions of the two species of microgreens (basil and lettuce) are specific to semi-controlled conditions, using the Eden Grow plant growing tent. Thus, a temperature was kept in the atmosphere with a maximum oscillation of 3-4 °C, an atmospheric humidity oscillation of 8-10 %, and respectively a constant amount of light (of 1217 $\mu\text{molm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). The irrigation water had a constant temperature of 19-21 °C, a pH of 6.8-7, an electrical conductivity between 1.4-1.5 mS, and respectively a quantity of 6.4-6.5 mg L^{-1} dissolved oxygen. Among the 2 species tested, lettuce ensures distinctly significantly positive Fresh Weight production. By comparison with the Duncan test, it results that the best amount of Fresh Weight is provided by Lettuce - Lolla Rossa, with 889.86 g/m^2 . Basil provides the highest amount of Dry Weight, with a very distinctly significantly positive difference. The variability of the data recorded for total phenols is very high, and the statistical processing did not highlight results with a significant difference. Lettuce contains 98-107.33 mg/kg , and basil 141-186.33 mg/kg total phenols. From the morphological analysis of plant development, both in basil and in lettuce, no disease attack is registered, due to the maintenance of the health of the water in the feed basin and a quantity of around 6.4-6.5 mg L^{-1} of dissolved oxygen. An exception is made in the case of lettuce, the Paris White variety, which registers until the end, grade 3 in the degree of attack. This is due exclusively to this variety in which the seed had an inadequate quality for the production of hydroponic microgreens. In conclusion, the experiment in the GOhydro platform, in semi-controlled conditions (plant growth tent) shows productive pathways to ensure an optimal development of hydroponically grown microgreens. It is very important to control vegetation factors, temperature, atmospheric humidity, etc. However, cultivation technology is very important. This resulted in some useful recommendations such as necessity to know and determine the actual germination of the seeds.

Following the work conducted in Work Package 1 with identifying ideal growing conditions using environmental controls for Microgreen production, we conducted controlled environment experiments in the pilot sites of Denmark and Romania to test and validate these previous results. In Denmark, we grew six different species of Microgreens: Basil, Coriander, Kale, Kohlrabi, Mustard, and Radish. These Microgreens were experimented on using multiple factors, such as Fertilization (yes or no), Light Recipe (of which there were five total recipes from two different types of lights), and Seeding Density (high and standard). The experiment was conducted as a complete random block design with highly controlled environmental conditions, such as air temperature, relative humidity, pH, EC, and light incidence. We showed that there were highly significant differences between all tested species, and as a result we conducted statistical analyses at a higher resolution to parse apart the influence of our different experimental factors on each individual species. Overall, we found much species-specific variation in accumulation of secondary metabolites due to experimental factors. However, we did find some general trends whereby Phenolic accumulation was best explained by Light Recipe: specifically, it was the High Far Red recipe which performed the best. However, there was a tradeoff in this case, as the High Far Red produced the most Phenolics, but also the least amount of Antioxidants. For Anthocyanins, we found it was more nuanced: we saw that light intensity, fertilization, and seeding density, depending on the species, explained the most variation. The same dynamic response was seen for Flavonoids as well. Therefore, these validation experiments have shown the sensitivity of these six different Microgreen species to different combinations of our experimental factors. Overall, we did not find any single best recipe, but we did identify species-specific responses and some general tradeoffs that were shown. These results can be instructive for producers that have specific production outcomes in mind, and can be used to tailor different efforts in combination with our previous deliverables on Microgreen production methodologies.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims at developing a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring hydroponically cultivated microgreens’ environmental parameters and nutrient content in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in many hydroponic installations. GOhydro aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

The purpose of the research made within WP4 concerns pilot trials in low-cost hydroponic units with a specific focus on the influence the environmental factors have on the growth and development of microgreens under hydroponic conditions. The hydroponic technology is analyzed with the goal to highlight, under the conditions of the GOhydro platform, in what way different environmental and nutritional factors can influence the development of microgreens and can improve its production and quality.

WP4 activity has 2 main objectives:

- To design the trial protocols for evaluating the GOhydro platform in realistic uncontrolled installations and in operational highly controlled settings;
- To carry out pilot trials and provide feedback for the refinement and calibration of the GOhydro platform.

Timetable of task components of WP4 are as follows:

Table 1.1: Timetable of task components of WP4				
Task	Month	Partners’ role	Activities	Deliverables
T4.1 Experimentation methodology for high-value nutrient design	[M10-M15] [01.12.2021-31.05.2022]	USAMV (lead), with participation of UCPH, SCiO, and NCSR-D	In formulating protocols, a minimum two of the four microgreens identified (basil, lettuce, coriander and mint) will be selected per location for testing in low-cost hydroponics units in Greece, Denmark and Romania. The protocols will define the data collection and data format to be followed, so that datasets generated in each trial site are comparable and combinable into a single, common dataset.	D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units (R, PU) [M15] A report detailing the methods, materials and hydroponic units to be used for the GOhydro trials both in controlled and operational settings.
T4.2 Experimentation in controlled realistic installations	[M13-M24] [01.03.2022-28.02.2023]	SCiO (lead), with participation of USAMV	The low-cost hydroponic units to be used will be capable of supporting the growth of approximately 80-100 plants per production cycle. The trials will take place in two sites, Greece and Romania, where each partner will test at least two crops to sample the different growing environments.	D4.2 Evaluation results from experiments in semi-controlled realistic installations (R, PU) [M21] A report presenting and analysing the results and insights gained from the pilots under controlled settings.

<p>T4.3 Validation of performance of low-cost hydroponic units in operational settings</p>	<p>[M19-M24] [01.09.2022-28.02.2023]</p>	<p>USAMV (lead), with participation of UCPH, SCiO, and NCSR-D</p>	<p>Production trials on the two identified microgreens in low-cost hydroponic units, will be carried out in Greece, Denmark and Romania in operational environments. The operational environments include office and living spaces for everyday use; the production parameters are not controlled. Feedback from these trials will be used for the final validation of the analytics components of the GOhydro platform.</p>	<p>D4.3 Report on validation of microgreens production in operational settings (R, PU) [M24] A report presenting and analysing the results and insights gained from the pilots under operational settings.</p>
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The purpose of this research is to analyze in detail certain elements relevant for the microgreens crop grown under hydroponic systems, such as (Moraru et al., 2022): air temperature, water temperature, humidity, pH, electrical conductivity, different nutrient solutions, and the influence of light regimes (quantity, quality, and photoperiods). This will situate growth regimes to allow for the control of diseases and pests and achieve desired growth and production trajectories. The goal of all these determinations is to contribute to the development of knowledge concerning the challenges of microgreens crops in a controlled hydroponic environment which will push forward discussions and practice in this segment of research and industry.

The experiments in semi-controlled realistic installations presented in Deliverable 4.2 are set up based on previous research seen in:

- Task 1.1 Review on nutrient and production parameters and light requirements (UCPH, SCiO, USAMV) [M1-M6];
- Task 1.2 Evaluation of optimised growth environments in controlled experiments and on the selection of promising recipes (UCPH & SCiO) [M4-M12];
- Task 4.1 Experimentation methodology for high-value nutrient design (USAMV, UCPH, SCiO, NCSR-D) [M10-M15];
- Task 4.2 Experimentation in controlled realistic installations (SCiO & USAMV) [M13-M24].

Furthermore, the protocols of deliverable D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units (R, PU) [M15], define the data collection procedures and data format organization to be followed, so that datasets generated in each trial site are comparable and combinable into a single, common dataset.

In order to meet the requirements of the project so that the datasets generated in each trial site are comparable and combinable into a single, common dataset, the following principles for the elaboration of the hydroponic microgreen production protocol were suggested:

- *IN CONTROLLED SETTINGS* – setting the optimal ranges of environmental parameters between the limits of favorability for each species, as seen in the literature review in D1.1, and validated in D1.2 experiments, for microgreens to highlight the effects of the GOhydro platform (Greece and Romania).

- Use of identical GOhydro prototypes - for comparable data:
 - Each pilot site (GREECE, DENMARK and ROMANIA) is responsible for setting up a hydroponic installation on its own by following the guidelines of deliverable D2.1;
 - GOhydro has provide identical sensor kits (Crop Heath Sensor Kit – CHSK and Nutrient Content Kit - NCK from Task 2.4). By Month 18 (August 2022) three sensor kits have been integrated and sent to the partners’ sites for testing within the framework of WP4.

- It is also important to use the same type of substrate for seed germination and growth, and to use the same variety of our common species (basil) in the three partner sites.

- Common protocols have been set for data collection, data formatting, and collection intervals.
- Data collection has been done using 3 repetitions.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION AT ROMANIAN PILOT SITE

The GOhydro platform was built considering the recommendations of *Deliverable 2.1 Multi-modal Sensor Kit Specifications and Requirements [M3]* (Table 4.1).

USAMV Cluj built 2 GOhydro platforms, identical, to be able to do experiments in parallel, both in semi-controlled conditions and in operational conditions. In this deliverable, the results obtained under semi-controlled conditions will be presented.

The construction stages of the GOhydro platform are presented in figure 2.1. We used the grow tent Eden Grow XL Growbox Growtent homegrowing 240x120x200 cm.

Figure 2.1: Construction of GOhydro platforms at USAMV

The GOhydro hydroponic platforms from USAMV Cluj-Napoca were built between February and October 2022, and each have the following components, systemically grouped:

- Structure Hydroponic System Storeyed Microgreens with 3 Trays (SHSM3T);
- System for Irrigation and Recirculation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM3T;
- System for lighting and automation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM3T.

The technical characteristics of the systems included in the GOhydro hydroponic platform are presented in tables 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3

Table 2.1: Technical Data Sheet - Structure Hydroponic System Storeyed Microgreens with 3 Trays		
No	Structure - SHSM3T	Characteristics
1	Number of modules SHSM3T	2
2	Type of structure	Demountable
3	Type of assembly	Demountable
4	Thickness of the system structure (mm)	20
5	Hydroponic system length (mm)	~ 800
6	Width hydroponic system (mm)	~ 450
7	Hydroponic system height (mm)	~ 1400
8	No. of floors of culture/module	3
9	Height to first floor (mm)	400

10	Distance between floors (mm)	300
11	No. of culture trays/module	3
12	Culture tray length (mm)	~ 670
13	Culture tray width (mm)	~ 320
14	Culture tray height (mm)	~ 30

Table 2.2: Technical Data Sheet - System for Irrigation and Recirculation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM₃T

No	System for Irrigation and Recirculation SHSM ₃ T	Characteristics
1	Number of modules SHSM ₃ T	2
2	Nutrient irrigation system	Drip 1 line
3	Type of structure	Demountable
4	Type of assembly	Demountable
5	Irrigation columns/module	3
6	Nutrient recirculation system	Modular
7	Recirculating columns nutrients/module	3
8	Nutrient recovery system	Modular
9	Nutrient recovery columns/module	3
10	Distributor recirculation system/module	1
11	Valves (repair/maintenance)/module	1
12	Irrigation pump and nutrient recirculation	1
13	Nutrient tank	1

Table 2.3: Technical Data Sheet - System for lighting and automation in Hydroponic Storeyed Microgreens SHSM₃T

No	System for lighting and automation S _H EM ₃ T	Characteristics
1	Number of modules SHSM ₃ T	2
2	Type of structure	Demountable
3	Type of assembly	Demountable
4	Lighting lamps	6
5	LED tube bulbs - 6500K - 18W	12
6	Lighting lamps/module	3
7	LED bulbs 6500K - 18W/module	6
8	Lighting control system/module	2
9	Lighting/floor control system	6
10	Nutrient aeration system	1
11	Nutrient aeration pump	1
12	Nutrient aeration pump control system	1
13	Irrigation/lighting automation	1
14	Automation control system/module	2

USAMV performed the test with the GOhydro platform in semi-controlled conditions, with 2 species: basil and lettuce.

The experimental conditions were:

1. For the basil:

Tray size (3): 64 cm x 31 cm = 1984 cm²

On each tray 2 varieties = 992 cm²:

- ✓ *Germaline Basilic Bio (Italiano classico)* = 3.84 g/tray (992 cm²)
- ✓ *Basil Grand Vert* = 3.78 g/tray (992 cm²)

Sowing date: 4/11/2022, 48 hours in the dark for germination
Substrate - hemp

2. For the lettuce:

Tray size (3): 64 cm x 31 cm = 1984 cm²

On each tray 3 varieties = 661 cm²:

- ✓ Paris White = 4.18 g/tray (661 cm²)
- ✓ Little Gem = 3.87 g/tray (661 cm²)
- ✓ Lolla Rossa = 3.98 g/tray (661 cm²)

Sowing date: 5/12/2022, 48 hours in the dark for germination
Substrate – hemp

The following devices were used for the measurements: Laserliner o82.130A LuxTest-Master Illumination Meter; wtw pH 315i - Digital pH Meter; Milwaukee Pro Portable Meters.

Drinking water used for irrigation has the following characteristics: pH=6.81, EC=261 μS/cm, TDS=389 ppm, Nitrites NO₂ = 0 mg/l, Nitrates NO₃ = 0 mg/l, Hardness = 14 °d

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION AT DANISH PILOT SITE

2.2.1 Experimental Conditions

This experiment was conducted in a walk-in ‘Conviron CMP5090’ climate chamber (Figure 2.2) with programmable conditions set to daily (24-hour) schedules located at the University of Copenhagen’s Taastrup Campus, Taastrup, Denmark. This climate chamber allowed for the control of temperature, airflow, and power inputs via its climate control system. We controlled humidity internally with a stand-alone device. Within the climate chamber, we constructed a six-tiered growing system, supplied by a commercial Microgreen producer (Instagreen.eu, Barcelona, Spain). The Instagreen grow system is 217.5 cm in height, 120 cm wide, and 112 cm deep. This growing system can hold up to 12 trays on six layers (2 trays per layer), with a total usable growing space of 7.26 m². Each growing tray has the dimensions of 110 (L) x 55 (W) x 5 (H) cm. 40 cups fit per tray, with each cup having a top dimension of 14.5 (L) x 10 (W) cm, with a narrower bottom dimension of 11.5 (L) x 8.2 (W) cm, and a cup height of 5 cm. The Instagreen setup is a modular system with variable-height layers that are tilted slightly to direct water flow via gravity after being pumped to the top-most layer from a reservoir. The solution then descends from one layer to the next via perforations in the bottom-most section of each tray and falls over a slide into the top of the next layer, until it returns to the reservoir. The reservoir holds approximately 40 liters of solution at a maximum.

a. Exterior of Conviron Climate Chamber

b. Water reservoir and pump for Danish grow system

c. Finished 6-layer grow system active

Figure 2.2: External and internal images of Danish pilot site climate chamber used for these controlled environment experiments.

Our experimental design was to use the upper three layers as light-treatment growing spaces as seen in Figure 2.2c, with the top-most layer using three OSRAM Phytofy Research Lights (Osram, Beverley, MA, USA) that were 41 cm from the emitters to the surface of the trays, the second layer being a buffer (or used when we had three generations running at once), and the third layer using four 1 meter long High Efficiency 24-volt LED (24VHELED) lights equidistant from one another which were 32 cm from the surface of the trays. The bottom three layers were used as germination space to ensure a successful transition for germination, growth, harvest, and starting the next generation. Each germination layer consisted of four standard growing trays, with two on the bottom, and two inverted on the top, to create a high-humidity dark-zone for adequate germination. Within our Climate Chamber we used a centralized utility box to ensure safe operations with electrical components shielded for use by growers and protected from water. In addition to the externally located climate control software, we also utilized two ‘Paladin pro4 Bluetooth’ timers which were located in the utility box inside the climate chamber. These were used to program schedules for the ‘Water Master 1800 liters/hour’ water pump and the 24VHELEDs using the ‘Save’n carry’ App for Android (Hugo-mueller.de). We programmed our grow system to be watered two times a day for 15 minutes, 8 hours apart during the 16 hour photoperiod, once at the beginning, and once 8 hours later. The 24VHELED lights were controlled using the second ‘Paladin pro4 Bluetooth’ timer, which ensures that the light has a 16 hour photoperiod parallel with the OSRAM light programming. Within our climate chamber we also used a ‘Plus Zap’ infrared bug zapper to control pest incidence. We also used a sanitizing floor mat that was filled with ‘Rodalon’ (active ingredients: chloride-based compounds) that is safe to use with plastics.

Within each block, there were two sowing densities (standard and high) for each of four Brassicaceae species for a total of 8 cups per block. We used a multi-factorial CRBD experimental design, as each of our five light treatments had two seeding densities over time, and each was treated with and without fertilizer. The first round of experiments was conducted from May 12th to July 11th, while the second round was conducted from August 21st to October 14th. For the Coriander and Basil, there was only one light recipe given the extended growing period required to produce them (16 days), but they were grown at two seeding densities (standard and high) with and without fertilization over the same time period as the Brassicaceae Microgreens.

2.2.2 Light Conditions

For our experimental setup, each layer in the grow system had three light treatment blocks: on layer 1, there were 3 OSRAM lights, with each one treated as a block; on layer 3, there were four lights, with 3 corresponding inter-light blocks of homogenous spectrum and intensity. The OSRAM lights have a max power draw of 150 Watts per fixture, with dimensions of 66.7 (W) x 29.9 (L) x 4.4 (H) cm per fixture. According to Osram, their lights have a total luminaire efficiency of 96.77%, with a total luminaire efficacy of 307936 $\mu\text{mol/s/W}$. Each emitter has a 0.1 Watt power draw. These lights have five channels with spectral peaks at 385 nm (UV-A, maximum emittance at 50 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), 450 nm (Blue, maximum emittance at 250 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), 521 nm (Green, maximum emittance at 100 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), 660 nm (Red, maximum emittance at 250 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), and 730 nm (Far-Red, maximum emittance at 100 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), each peak of which can be set independently as a percent (0-100%) of its total output. There is also a sixth 'White' LED channel, which has a color temperature of 2,700 Kelvin, which is classified as between 'Sunrise and Sunset,' and has a maximum emittance of 250 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$. Therefore, the total maximum PFD for the OSRAM research light is 1000 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$. Our second type of lights used four 'Fullwat DOMOX line high efficiency 24-Volt' (Fullwat, Spain) LED light strips. These 24VHELED lights have a light color temperature of 4,000 Kelvin, which is classified as near direct sunlight (4,800 K), their output is 1380 lumens/m, their power is 12 W/m, they have an IP of 65 (water resistant), and a Color Rendering Index ≥ 83 .

Figure 2.3 below shows the OSRAM lights under a programmed light recipe, with the second panel (b) showing what the software looks like at the interface level. Figure 2.4 demonstrates the visualizations of the light recipes used in our experiments. They show in detail the proportional contribution of each wavelength of light (in nanometers, nm), on the x-axis, to the overall recipe. The y-axis is a unitless scale (0-100%), which demonstrates the relative proportion of each nm of light compared to the maximum value. The white lines in each figure demonstrate the irradiance (W/m^2) of each light recipe, while the black curve shows the PFD, which considers the number of photons. This is an important demonstration of the difference between the light recipes, as they have similar numbers of photons per unit area, with the four OSRAM light recipes having 181 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$ and the 24VHELEDs having around 40 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$, but the Irradiance (energy) of the recipes differ based on their light components, as seen by the differing white line curves in the figures.

a. OSRAM Phytofy lights in operation

b. Phytofy software detailing the programs monitoring of the lights in figure 2.3a

Figure 2.3: Detailed images of Danish pilot site OSRAM programmable lights and their corresponding Phytofy program used to control the light recipes. Figure b details the orientation of the lights, the spectral outputs, the light intensity ($\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$), the photoperiod (hours), and the daily light integral ($\text{mol/m}^2/\text{day}$).

Figure 2.4: Figures showing the relative values of irradiance (white lines) and PFD (black lines) for each light recipe used in Danish pilot site experiments. CRBD is Complete Random Block Design (CRBD), as these are derived from the spectrometric readings taken at the CRBD positions used in our experiments.

2.2.3 Plant Material

Our genetic stock used for these experiments consisted of four species of Brassicaceae and two herbaceous ones (Cilantro and Basil) which we grew from seeds. These were purchased from Instagreen (Instagreen.eu, Barcelona, Spain), a commercial Microgreens production company. Specifically, we chose to experiment on the following Brassicaceae species: Mustard (*Sinapis alba* cv. White Candy), Kale (*Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica* L. cv. Black Mandingo), Radish (*Brassica oleracea* cv. Daikon Panzer), and Kohlrabi (*Brassica oleracea* convar. *Acephala* var. *gongylodes* L. cv. Red Cardinal). The herbaceous species were Basil (*Osimum basilicum* var. Green Tesla) and Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* var. Green Thunder). The seed names, their seeding density, 100 seed weight, and estimated seeds per cup for each sowing density can be seen in Table 2.4. These values are shown as a mean +/- the SE. The percent of seeds that were germinated were counted as well for each Brassicaceae species over time. The value shown in Table 2.4 is the final germination value at harvest to detail the total achieved germination, eight days after sowing. Table 2.4 also shows the estimated amount of seeds per cup for our two different seeding densities (Standard and High). Overall, this table shows that we achieved very good germination results for all Brassicaceae Microgreens at around 99%, while for Kohlrabi, the germination rate was around 91.5%. This was likely due to the seed source. However, overall we saw very good, uniform production of Kohlrabi, and it was not thought to impact the results, especially considering the low standard error for Kohlrabi germination rate.

Table 2.4: 100 seed weights (+/- standard error), seeding densities in grams per cup and estimated number of seeds per cup at standard and high densities, estimated seeds per cm², and germination percentage (+/- standard error) are shown.

	100 Seed Weight (g)	Standard (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Seeds per cm ²	High (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Seeds per cm ²	Germ %
Kohlrabi	0.161 ± 0.005	1.5	929.37	6.41	2.25	1394.05	9.61	91.45 ± 0.36
Kale	0.313 ± 0.004	2.3	735.76	5.07	4	1279.59	8.82	97.85 ± 1.52
Mustard	0.720 ± 0.011	3	416.90	2.88	4.5	625.35	4.31	99.81 ± 0.03
Radish	1.325 ± 0.021	4	301.84	2.08	6	452.76	3.12	99.69 ± 0.05
Coriander	0.90 ± 0.01	1	556.02	3.83	1.5	834.03	5.75	ND
Basil	0.13 ± 0.001	5	759.49	5.24	7.5	1139.24	7.86	ND

For our experiment, the seeds were sown in plastic cups, with dimensions of 10 x 14.5 x 5 cm, on 100% cellulose growing pads according to sowing densities listed in Table 2.4. The substrate was soaked until saturated with distilled water prior to sowing. None of the Brassicaceae seeds were pre-soaked, but the Coriander seeds were soaked for 24 hours. After sowing seeds onto the soaked substrate, they were misted for approximately 1 second with distilled water to ensure initial moisture at the superior surface of the seeds. Our substrate was not compensated with a top-weight over the seeds, which was crucial for allowing the seedlings unimpeded vertical growth potential for short dark-zone germination and development time of 4 days for the Brassicaceae, and 16 days for the Cilantro and Basil. After sowing, each of the 8 cups (per block) were allocated according to a Complete Random Block Design (CRBD) for every light treatment. After this 4 day dark-germination period for the Brassicaceae, the plants were put under the lights for 4 days of light treatments, and were therefore harvested 8 days after sowing. For the Coriander and Basil, we grew them for 8 days in the dark, and 8 days under the light, for a total growing period of 16 days. Figures 2.5 and 2.6 below demonstrate the Microgreens grown in these experiments in their real conditions during the growing period.

a. OSRAM lights on (layer 1) in our grow system with four species of Brassicaceae

b. 24VHELEDs on (layer 2) for our second set of experiments on Cilantro and Basil Microgreens

Figure 2.5: Images of our Brassicaceae Microgreens grown under a High Red light recipe with OSRAM lights (a) and of the herbaceous Microgreens grown with the 24VHELEDs (b)

Figure 2.6: Photo at time of harvest for Danish pilot site four different species of Microgreens. Each species is labeled with its common name to show the distinctive qualities of each, namely their size and coloration.

2.2.4 Environmental Conditions

To measure and record relative humidity (%) and air temperature (°C) we used two ‘TinyTag View2 Loggers’ (Gemini Data Loggers, UK), one located between layers 1 and 3, and the second between layer 4 and 6 of our grow system to monitor changes in climate chamber microclimate. We used a ‘HOBO MX CO2 Logger’ (Onset, USA) to measure CO2 in our climate chamber. We also used a ‘HOBO Onset Pendant temp/light Logger’ (Onset, USA) to measure the amount of light (in lux units) and temperature directly under the OSRAM lights. Figure 2.7 below details the information collected from these devices for the first portion of our experiments: they show, from top to bottom, the CO2 concentration (ppm), the Relative Humidity (%), and the temperature (°C). Overall, these panels in Figure 2.7 show that we achieved relatively stable environmental conditions. The variation in CO2 was due to human activity in the climate chambers, but these spikes were quickly reduced down to their average value via air circulation. The RH also had some spikes due to our method of controlling humidity; however, conditions were stably kept around 65%, which was our set point. The temperature was also relatively stable, although we did have a few weeks of heatwaves that caused temporary spikes in temperature, but it was not hotter than 23 degrees.

Table 2.5 demonstrates the average environmental conditions, with standard error to show the variability, of our parameters of interest: temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), dew point (°C), CO2 (parts per million; ppm), and electrical conductivity (EC, mS/cm). We can see here that the average temperature was essentially highly controlled over time, with very minor deviations. For relative humidity, we can see that the fertilized conditions were drier on average than the non-fertilized, due to parameterization of humidity control early on in the experimental process. As a result, the dew point was also lower for the fertilized experiments. The CO2 was also essentially the same for Fertilized and Non-fertilized treatments, with small errors due to the influence of employee CO2 additions when in close proximity to the plants. According to parameterization, the pH was more often controlled, and was therefore lower when fertilizer was applied, which was a necessity to ensure the adequate uptake of nutrients. The Non-fertilized experiments had less pH management, and it was therefore higher overall. For EC, the Fertilized experiments were right around the set point of 1.8 mS/cm, as seen in Table 2.6 in the next section on Fertilization details. The Non-fertilized (tap water) solution had an average EC of 0.81, which was higher than pure tap water, likely as a result of the addition of acid to lower the pH. We controlled pH in the Non-fertilized conditions to keep it, in general, under 7, and to keep it in a general range of the Fertilized pH conditions, so that they would be comparable growing environments.

Table 2.5: Means +/- standard error for temperature, relative humidity, dew point, CO2, pH, EC for fertilized and non-fertilized treatments that were used for our secondary metabolite experiments.

Treatment	Temperature	Relative Humidity	Dew Point	CO2	pH	EC
Fertilized	21.65 ± 0.01	63.93 ± 0.34	14.41 ± 0.07	485.4 ± 3.26	6.2 ± 0.09	1.71 ± 0.04
Non-Fertilized	21.67 ± 0.01	69.93 ± 0.27	15.85 ± 0.06	481.8 ± 2.47	6.6 ± 0.19	0.81 ± 0.01

Figure 2.7: Panels showing the CO2 concentration (top panel, parts per million), relative humidity (middle panel, %), and temperature (bottom panel, °C) for the high zone sensor location. X-axis shows the date for all three panels.

2.2.5 Fertilization

For the fertilization component of our experiment, we used Pioneer NPK (Mg) Macro Blue 14-3-23 (3) (Pioneer, Denmark) for our macro nutrient fertilizer; for our micronutrient fertilizer, we used Pioneer Micro with Iron (Pioneer, Denmark). For the concentrated fertilizer solution, we used 10 kgs of Macro per 100 L of water, and 1 L of Micro per 100 L of water. For use in our hydroponic system, this was applied at 15% dilution for a rate of 85 mL of concentrated nutrient solution per 10 Liters of water. Table 2.6 details the initial percentages for both Macro and Micro solutions, and their corresponding concentration (in ppm) in our hydroponic solution. In addition, we used Nitric Acid to control our pH, with a Nutrient Solution pH target of 6.0. For EC, we did not modify it after achieving an initial value, with fertilization, of around of 1.8 mS/cm, according to our NS dilution. However, the pH was controlled daily with additional acid supplementation, which was necessary due to the high chalk (Calcium Carbonate, CaCO₃) content of Danish tap water. As water evaporates after irrigation runs as a result of our ebb and flow system, it slowly deposits chalk on the trays, which increases the concentration of chalk after proceeding irrigation runs. Therefore, after every eight days (the generation time for the Microgreens) the system was drained of all solution, cleaned and scrubbed of chalk residue, and reset with either Tap Water + Acid, or Tap Water + Fertilizer + Acid to obtain our pH and EC targets. This was done for both generations using fertilized NS and for unfertilized solution. For measuring pH and Electrical Conductivity (EC, mS/cm), we used a Mesur Hand Instrument (Senmatic DGT-Voltmatic, Denmark), which has a sensitivity for pH of 0.1, and for EC has a sensitivity of 0.01 for EC values under 2.5 mS/cm.

Table 2.6: Fertilization details for the different macro- and micro-nutrient products used. Here we show the name, elemental sign, original concentration (%), and concentration in solution (ppm).

<i>Pioneer NPK (Mg) Macro Blue 14-3-23 (3)</i>			
Description	Element	Original Concentration (%)	PPM in solution
Total Nitrogen	N	14.00%	119
Nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻	10.40%	88.4
Ammonium	NH ₄ ⁺	3.60%	30.6
Water soluble Phosphorous	P	2.90%	24.65
Citric and water soluble Phosphorous	P	2.90%	24.65
Water soluble Potassium	K	23.00%	195.5
Water soluble Magnesium	Mg	3.00%	25.5
Water soluble Sulphur	S	3.90%	33.15
Chloride	Cl	0.50%	4.25
Fluoride	F	0.50%	4.25
Calcium (CaCO ₃ , Chalk, in Danish Tap Water)	Ca	X	~300
EC (mS/cm)		1.78	

<i>Pioneer Micro with Iron</i>			
Description	Element	Original Concentration (%)	PPM in solution
Boron	B	0.23%	0.1955
Copper	Cu	0.14%	0.119
Iron	Fe	1.32%	1.122
Manganese	Mn	0.50%	0.425
Molybdenum	Mo	0.05%	0.0425
Zinc	Zn	0.18%	0.153
EC (mS/cm)		0.006	
Total EC (mS/cm)		1.786	

2.2.6 Secondary Metabolite Methodology

For our secondary metabolite analysis, we first measured the Fresh Weight of each cup. Then around 5 grams of material was separated and immediately allocated to the -20 °C freezer for future analyses. Our samples were analyzed at the University of Copenhagen's Taastrup Lab. At this lab, our frozen samples were placed in liquid nitrogen after being removed from the freezer. They were then ground and allocated into 100 mg test tubes. They were then weighed and put back in the freezer until it was time for the assays. At this time, the samples were taken out and were subjected to secondary metabolite analyses for Anthocyanins, Flavonoids, Phenolics, and Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC). A standard curve was measured for each plate (containing 20 samples) where necessary to which our samples were compared to obtain our secondary metabolite values.

Figure 2.8: Image of Mustard Microgreens at time of harvest. Each cup was a replicate for our study, and the entire cup was harvested and weighed before being allocated to the freezer for future assays.

2.3 EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION AT GREEK PILOT SITE

2.3.1 Experimental Conditions

The experiments carried out at the Greek Pilot Site focused on the testing of the Nutrient Content Kit (NCK, details in D2.2), the development of the measuring protocols and the verification of the proof-of-concept. This feasibility study was developed with the following underlying idea: to create an affordable and accessible hydroponic installation with personalized monitoring for use in any urban setting, even by non-professionals. All components must be off-the-shelf, affordable, and easily ordered online, while the installation can be assembled in a do-it-yourself (DIY) manner. The optical biosensing platform should be portable and autonomous, and the optical sensors reusable. The measuring process should be simple, cost-efficient, and performed in a room or office, with easily accessible reagents.

Towards that end, the hydroponic installation at the Greek Pilot Site was a totally DIY wick-type installation built by off-the shelf components ordered online (more details in D2.1) at the office premises of the co-ordinator

(SCiO). Seeds for *ocimum basilicum* (small-leaf basil, hereafter referred to as “small-leaf” for brevity), *ocimum basilicum* “mammoth” (wide-leaf basil, hereafter referred to as “mammoth” for brevity), *ocimum basilicum purpurescens* (purple basil hereafter re-ferred to as “purpurescens” for brevity) and *brassica oleracea var. italica* (broccoli, hereafter referred to as “broccoli” for brevity) were purchased by a local plant store. Simple tap water was used to water the plants without the use of any nutrient powders. No special light conditions were used apart from the lamp installed in the hydroponic tent.

Initially, two types of basil (small-leaf and mammoth) were planted in order to familiarize ourselves with hydroponics, to test for appropriate solvents, and to devise an appropriate yet simple protocol for measuring the plant extracts with the immersible sensors. The purpose was to determine if the plant extracts could be measured accurately using the immersible sensors and to establish familiarity with hydroponics. This first test was described in length in D2.2, where it was shown that even though the NCK could in principle differentiate between the two basil species, the chosen solvent (acetone) was not appropriate. New tests were conducted with different solvents (pure ethanol and a mixture of ethanol-water) as well as cleaning protocols to establish the re-usability of the immersible photonic sensors.

Afterwards, all available plants (including all three types of basil and broccoli) were hydroponically cultured and harvested 10 days after seeding. This round of harvest was used to determine if differentiation among different plants and among plants of the same species could be achieved by the sensors. Subsequently, basil was chosen as a study case and the edible species of small-leaf and mammoth basil were grown for a total of 3 weeks. The scope of this round was to investigate whether the NCK could provide indirect information about the optimum harvest time. Portions of the basil microgreens were harvested at 1-week intervals and each sample was split in half. One half was immediately transported to the Agricultural University of Athens for measurement using standard analytical techniques that would determine the total phenolic content and antioxidant activity, while the other half was measured using the immersible sensor setup. To maintain freshness, the microgreens were stored in a freezer at -20°C until testing.

2.3.2 Optimization of Measuring Protocol

As described in D2.2, the first attempt to produce microgreen extracts for use with the NCK was based on a thorough literature research (WP1). Sample preparation for plant studies revealed the prevalent use of acetone and alcohols (methanol or ethanol) in conjunction with fresh plant samples. Acetone and ethanol were chosen as solvents to be tested, and a straightforward sample preparation method was devised. This method involved homogenizing the collected samples in the respective solvent with the aid of a standard pestle and mortar, transferring the resulting pulp into a syringe, and obtaining the “extract” by filtration through a 400 µm pore filter (see also D2.2). The plant extracts as well as the various solvents used to test the rinsing process were placed in 5 mL Eppendorf tubes placed in a suitable holder

The initial findings of D2.2 determined that acetone was not a suitable solvent to prepare basil extracts, because (1) it induced large shifts to the baseline, and (2) could not completely remove (rinse) the adhered molecules from the sensor surface. Consequently, the suitability of ethanol as a solvent was investigated, accompanied by a reduction in plant concentration to 1g per 5mL of solvent. The potential formation of adlayers on the sensor surface prompted not only the plant concentration reduction, but also the implementation of a more rigorous rinsing protocol, akin to regeneration methods employed by the NCSR-D team in biodetection schemes. The measurement steps involved sequential treatment with ethanol (to establish a baseline), plant extract, ethanol (for rinsing), DI water (to remove ethanol residue), 100 mM HCl in DI water (to eliminate any adlayers), DI water (for acid rinse), and ethanol (to ensure complete rinsing and restore baseline). Multiple cycles of these measurements were performed to assess chip cleanliness, reusability, and consistency of results, thereby determining the extent of sustainable reusability. This study was performed with all four plants (small-leaf, mammoth, purpurescens and broccoli) harvested 10 days after seeding from the DIY hydroponic installation.

Figure 2.9 presents the comprehensive sequential experiments conducted to simultaneously assess the suitability of ethanol as a solvent and the repeatability of measurements. The consolidated findings are summarized in Figure 2.10, where the transitions from ethanol to plant extract in repeated cycles are plotted for all plants. Notably, ethanol established a reliable baseline with no observed shifts, distinguishing it from acetone. However, among the tested plants, repeatable results were achieved up to 4 rinsing cycles only for broccoli (Fig. 2.10d), up to 2 cycles for purpurescens (Fig. 2.10c), while both mammoth and small-leaf basil failed to deliver consistent results beyond the initial rinsing step (Fig. 2.10a and 2.10b, respectively). The most important result though lies in the distinct phase signals exhibited by the four plants, acquired from the initial immersion (1st cycle) of "fresh" immersible sensors, characterized by unique slopes indicative of each plant (Fig. 2.10e). This outcome supports the original hypothesis that the proposed approach has the capability to differentiate between different plants, even within the same species.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 2.9: Repeating cycles of testing and rinsing with pure ethanol used as the solvent and baseline for (a) mammoth basil, (b) small-leaf basil, (c) purple basil and (d) broccoli.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 2.10: Phase signal changes of ethanol-to-plant extract immersion after repeating cycles of dipping and rinsing for (a) mammoth basil, (b) small-leaf basil, (c) purpurescens basil, and (d) broccoli. (e) Comparison of the phase change signals from each plant after the first dipping of a pristine pho-tonic sensor (mammoth: blue line; small-leaf: green line; purpurescens: magenta line; broccoli: orange line).

Upon closer examination of the signals in Figure 2.9 , it became obvious that the additional step of rinsing with water and hydrochloric acid may not be necessary. Furthermore, during the measurements, it was observed that ethanol evaporated rapidly and needed to be replenished multiple times. In line with the objective of maintaining a simple measurement protocol with minimal materials, we adopted a simplified approach. A mixture of 30% v/v DI water and 70% v/v ethanol was utilized as a baseline and as the solvent for mashing the plant, followed by immersing the sensor in the plant extracts and rinsing with pure ethanol until the signal stabilized. This simplified approach was tested with 2-week-old microgreens of mammoth and small-leaf basil. As depicted in Figure 2.11, this simplified approach surprisingly yielded repeatable signals for up to four testing–rinsing cycles. This approach was finally chosen to perform the final proof-of-concept experiments.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.11: Consolidated phase change signals from 5 repeated cycles of ethanol–water/basil extract/ethanol for (a) mammoth and (b) small-leaf basil. Arrows indicate the transition from one liquid sample to the next.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 RESULTS IN ROMANIA

3.1.1 Data obtained in the experiments with basil and lettuce

The methodology used for the research was the one described in the deliverable D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units. The images of the two experiments are presented in Figure 3.1 (basil) and Figure 3.2 (lettuce).

Figure 3.1: Images of the experiment with basil in semi-controlled conditions

Figure 3.2: Images of the experiment with lettuce in semi-controlled conditions

The raw data collected from the two experiments are presented in table 3.1 and table 3.3 for basil and in table 3.2 and table 3.4 for lettuce.

Table 3.1: Parameters collected related to the growth environment in the basil experiment

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Specification	Day 1 /4.11	Day 2 /5.11	Day 3 /6.11	Day 4 /7.11	Day 5 /8.11	Day 6 /9.11	Day 7 /10.11	Day 8 /11.11	Day 9 /12.11	Day 10 /13.11	Day 11 /14.11	Day 12 /15.11	Day 13 /16.11	Day 14 /17.11	Day 15 /18.11	Day 16 /19.11	Day 17 /20.11	Day 18 /21.11	
A. Monitoring the environmental conditions – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK)																					
Air Temperature Sensor*	°C	min/max/mean	19/23/21	19/24/22	19/24/22	20/24/22	21/25/23	20/24/22	19/24/22	20/23/22	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/23/22	19/23/21	19/23/21	20/23/22	19/23/21	19/23/21	19/23/21	19/23/21
Air Humidity Sensor*	%	min/max/mean	60/68/64	60/69/65	60/69/65	61/69/65	60/70/65	59/68/64	60/70/65	59/68/64	59/68/64	59/67/62	59/67/62	59/68/64	60/68/64	59/68/64	59/68/64	60/68/64	60/68/64	60/68/64	60/68/64
Light Sensor (UV)	µmolm-2s-1	lux	-	-	-	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217
B. Monitoring the water and nutrient quality – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK) and Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)																					
Water Temperature Sensor	°C	min/max/mean	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20
Digital pH Meter***	pH units		6.8	6.8	6.8	6.9	6.9	7.0	7.0	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9
Electroconductivity Sensor	mS		1.4	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	
Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)	Nutrient content	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dissolved oxygen	mgL-1		6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.8	6.6	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3	

Table 3.2: Parameters collected related to the growth environment in the lettuce experiment

Parameter	Unit of measurement	Specification	Day 1 /5.12	Day 2 /6.12	Day 3 /7.12	Day 4 /8.12	Day 5 /9.12	Day 6 /10.12	Day 7 /11.12	Day 8 /12.12	Day 9 /13.12	Day 10 /14.12	Day 11 /15.12	Day 12 /16.12	Day 13 /17.12	Day 14 /18.12	Day 15 /19.12	
A. Monitoring the environmental conditions – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK)																		
Air Temperature Sensor*	°C	min/max/mean	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	21/23/22	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21
Air Humidity Sensor*	%	min/max/mean	57/60/63	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	56/58/57	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55	54/56/55
Light Sensor (UV)	µmolm-2s-1	lux	-	-	-	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	1217	
B. Monitoring the water and nutrient quality – by Crop Heath Sensor Kit (CHSK) and Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)																		
Water Temperature Sensor	°C	min/max/mean	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	19/21/20	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	21/23/22	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/22/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21	20/21/21
Digital pH Meter	pH units		6.8	6.8	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	
Electroconductivity Sensor	mS		1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	
Nutrient Content Kit (NCK)	Nutrient content	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Dissolved oxygen	mgL-1		6.5	6.4	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.4	

Note: * Drinking water measurements: pH=6.81, EC=261 µS/cm, TDS=389 ppm, Nitrites NO₂ = 0 mg/l, Nitrates NO₃ = 0 mg/l, Hardness = 14 °d

Table 3.3: Parameters related to microgreen growth, production and quality in the basil experiment			
Parameter	Unit of measurement	Day 18/21.11	Day 18/21.11
Determining the health state of plants		Germaline	Grand Vert
Intensity of the disease attack	Note 1-9	1	1
Measurements on the morphology of plants*		r1/r2/r3	r1/r2/r3
Stem length	mm	31.2/32.1/32.1	25.2/25.4/25.2
Internode length	mm	31.2/32.1/32.1	25.2/25.4/25.2
Number of leaves	no	2 / 2 / 2	2 / 2 / 2
Number of plants	no/cm ²	10.2 / 10.6 / 9.9	8.7 / 9.1 / 8.9
Leaves area (10 plants per tray)	cm ²	0.52 / 0.54 / 0.52	0.49 / 0.52 / 0.51
Determining Fresh Biomass Yield and Dry Matter Content			
Fresh Weight	g tray (992 cm ²)	78.45/76.84/77.89	68.12/68.45/67.56
Dry Weight	g tray (992 cm ²)	7.79/7.69/7.81	6.78/6.81/6.78
Total phenols	mg/kg	115/169/139	172/114/273

Note: r1- top tray; r2 - middle tray; r3 - bottom tray

Table 3.4: Parameters related to microgreen growth, production and quality in the lettuce experiment				
Parameter	Unit of measurement	Day 15 /19.12	Day 15/19.12	Day 15/19.12
Determining the health state of plants		Paris White	Little Gem	Lolla Rossa
Intensity of the disease attack	Note 1-9	3	1	1
Measurements on the morphology of plants*		r1/r2/r3	r1/r2/r3	r1/r2/r3
Stem length	mm	0/0/0	30.4/31.1/30.2	31.4/31.8/31.9
Internode length	mm	0/0/0	30.4/31.1/30.2	31.4/31.8/31.9
Number of leaves	no	0/0/0	2.5/2.4/2.6	2.3/2.1/2.2
Number of plants	no/cm ²	0/0/0	10.1/10.4/10.2	9.1/9.1/9.4
Leaves area (10 plants per tray)	cm ²	0/0/0	0.49/0.50/0.51	0.62/0.61/0.62
Determining Fresh Biomass Yield and Dry Matter Content				
Fresh Weight	g tray (661 cm ²)	0/0/0	48.45/47.84/48.32	58.45/59.12/58.89
Dry Weight	g tray (661 cm ²)	0/0/0	3.35/3.31/3.35	4.05/4.10/4.08
Total phenols	mg/kg	0/0/0	99/98/97	114/101/107

Note: r1- top tray; r2 - middle tray; r3 - bottom tray

The growing conditions of the two species of microgreens (basil and lettuce) are specific to semi-controlled conditions, using the Eden Grow plant growing tent. Thus, a temperature was kept in the atmosphere with a maximum oscillation of 3-4 °C, an atmospheric humidity oscillation of 8-10 %, and respectively a constant amount of light (of 1217 $\mu\text{molm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$).

The irrigation water had a constant temperature of 19-21 °C, a pH of 6.8-7, an electrical conductivity between 1.4-1.5 mS, and respectively a quantity of 6.4-6.5 mg L⁻¹ dissolved oxygen.

No nutrients were used for fertigation.

3.1.2 Fresh Weight Accumulation

The amount of Fresh Weight (FW) depends on both the cultivated species and the variety (Table 3.5), respectively its suitability for hydroponic microgreens. Among the 2 species tested, lettuce ensures distinctly significantly positive Fresh Weight production (Table 3.6). By comparison with the Duncan test, it results that the best amount of Fresh Weight is provided by Lettuce - Lolla Rossa, with 889.86 g/m².

Table 3.5: The amount of Fresh Weight Accumulation in the two species (basil and lettuce) and varieties

Species	Variety	Repetition (g/m ²)		
		R1	R2	R3
Basil	Germaline Basilic Bio	790.83	774.60	785.18
	Grand Vert	686.69	690.02	681.05
Lettuce	Little Gem	732.98	723.75	731.01
	Lolla Rossa	884.27	894.40	890.92

Table 3.6: The influence of the species on the amount of Fresh Weight Accumulation

Species	Fresh Weight		Difference ±	Significance
	g/m ²	%		
Control	772.14	100	Ct.	Ct.
Basil	734.73	95.2	-37.41	00
Lettuce	809.56	104.8	37.41	**

Note: DL (p 5%)= 10.75 g/m²; DL (p 1%)= 24.83 g/m²; DL(p 0.1%)= 79.02 g/m²

Table 3.7: Synthesis of comparisons through the Duncan test

Species and variety	Fresh Weight, g/m ²	Classification
Basil - Grand Vert	685.92	a
Lettuce - Little Gem	729.25	b
Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio	783.54	c
Lettuce - Lolla Rossa	889.86	d

3.1.3 Dry Weight Accumulation

Following the statistical processing of the data (ANOVA) regarding Dry Weight Accumulation, it is found that the results differ from Fresh Weight. The results obtained on the repetitions (GOhydro platform trays) are presented in the Table 3.8. Basil provides the highest amount of Dry Weight (DW) (Table 3.9), with a very distinctly significantly positive difference compared to the control. The same results after processing the data with the Duncan test, respectively the 2 varieties of basil ensure the highest Dry Weight results (Table 3.10).

Table 3.8: The amount of Dry Weight Accumulation in the two species (basil and lettuce) and varieties

Species	Variety	Repetition (g/m ²)		
		R1	R2	R3
Basil	Germaline Basilic Bio	78.53	77.52	78.73
	Grand Vert	68.35	68.65	68.35
Lettuce	Little Gem	50.68	50.08	50.68
	Lolla Rossa	61.27	62.03	61.72

Table 3.9: The influence of the species on the amount of Dry Weight Accumulation

Species	Dry Weight		Difference ±	Significance
	g/m ²	%		
Control	64.72	100	Ct.	Ct.
Basil	73.36	113.3	8.64	***
Lettuce	56.08	86.7	-8.64	000

Note: DL (p 5%)= 0.56 g/m²; DL (p 1%)= 1.28 g/m²; DL(p 0.1%)= 4.09 g/m²

Table 3.10: Synthesis of comparisons through the Duncan test

Species and variety	Dry Weight, g/m ²	Classification
Lettuce - Little Gem	50.48	a
Lettuce - Lolla Rossa	61.67	b
Basil - Grand Vert	68.45	c
Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio	78.26	d

3.1.4 Total Phenolics/Morphology

The results obtained in the case of total phenols are presented in the Table 3.11. The variability of the data recorded for total phenols is very high, the statistical processing does not highlight results with a significant difference (Table 3.12). Lettuce contains 98-107.33 mg/kg, and basil 141-186.33 mg/kg total phenols (Table 3.13).

Table 3.11: The amount of total phenols in the two species (basil and lettuce) and varieties

Species	Variety	Repetition (mg/kg)		
		R1	R2	R3
Basil	Germaline Basilic Bio	115	169	139
	Grand Vert	172	114	273
Lettuce	Little Gem	99	98	97
	Lolla Rossa	114	101	107

Table 3.12: The influence of the species on the amount of total phenols

Species	Total phenols		Difference ±	Significance
	mg/kg	%		
Control	133.17	100	Ct.	Ct.
Basil	163.67	122.9	30.50	-
Lettuce	102.67	77.1	-30.50	-

Note: DL (p 5%)= 92.66 g/m²; DL (p 1%)= 213.98 g/m²; DL(p 0.1%)= 680.93 g/m²

Table 3.13: Synthesis of comparisons through the Duncan test

Species and variety	Total phenols, mg/kg	Classification
Lettuce - Little Gem	98.00	a
Lettuce - Lolla Rossa	107.33	a
Basil - Grand Vert	141.00	a
Basil - Germaline Basilic Bio	186.33	a

From the morphological analysis of plant development, both in basil and in lettuce, no disease attack is registered, due to the maintenance of the health of the water in the feed basin and a quantity of around 6.4-6.5 mg L⁻¹ of dissolved oxygen. An exception is made in the case of lettuce, the Paris White variety, which registers until the end, grade 3 in the degree of attack. This is due exclusively to this variety in which the seed had an inadequate quality for the production of hydroponic microgreens. There are differences regarding the

number of leaves, the length of the microgreens, etc. but these are given in particular by the variety used. Within the same variety, the differences between repetitions were very small, insignificant.

In conclusion, the experiment in the GOhydro platform, in semi-controlled conditions (plant growth tent) ensures an optimal development of hydroponic microgreens. Very important is the control of vegetation factors, temperature, atmospheric humidity, etc. However, cultivation technology is very important. This resulted in some useful recommendations: it is necessary to know / determine the actual germination of the seeds; the seeds must first be sterilized by soaking for 2 minutes in 80% ethanol, rinsed twice with distilled water and then dried in an oven at 45°C for 40 minutes; it is necessary to moisten the seeds beforehand, etc.

3.2 RESULTS IN DENMARK

3.2.1 Grouped ANOVA Results

For our first level of analysis, we ran an ANOVA on the entire Brassicaceae experimental dataset without separating by species. Table 3.14 demonstrates the overview of our grouped-dataset analysis. Overall, for Phenolics, there was a highly significant effect of species ($p < 0.001$), which necessitates further separated analyses. For Phenolics, our overall results demonstrated that there was a highly significant effect of Light Recipe by Seeding Density ($p < 0.001$), as well as Fertilizer by Seeding Density ($p = 0.01$). This indicates that the accumulation of Phenolics was dependent on the species, and the interaction between light recipe by fertilizer and fertilization at different seeding densities. For Flavonoids, there was also a highly significant species effect ($p < 0.001$); similarly to Phenolics, there was also a significant Light Recipe by Fertilizer interaction effect ($p < 0.001$). This was the highest order significant effect; Seeding Density on its own was also significant ($p = 0.02$). For Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC), there was once again a highly significant Species effect ($p < 0.001$), with two higher order significant effects for Light Recipe by Fertilizer ($p < 0.001$), and Light Recipe by Seeding Density ($p < 0.001$). For Anthocyanins, Species was also highly significant ($p < 0.001$), with two higher order interactions for Fertilizer by Seeding Density ($p = 0.03$), and Light Recipe by Seeding Density ($p = 0.01$). Overall, the most consistent result was the significance of Light Recipe interacting with Fertilizer influencing the accumulation of these secondary metabolites.

Table 3.14: ANOVA results for grouped Brassicaceae Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent/gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Total Effects	Phenolics	Flavonoids	Trolox equivalent	Anthocyanins
	P-Value	P-Value	antioxidant capacity P-Value	P-Value
Species	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Light Recipe	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.01
Fertilizer	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.03	0.12
Seeding Density	0.53	0.02	0.21	0.05
Light Recipe:Fertilizer	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.90
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.01	0.73	0.54	0.03
Light Recipe:Seeding Density	0.36	0.46	< 0.001	0.01
Light Recipe:Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.79	0.13	0.35	1.00

Table 3.15 offers a broad overview of the grouped means of our six different species used in our experiments for the four secondary metabolites. They show overall that Mustard had the highest level of Phenolics, with Coriander having the lowest; for Flavonoids, Kohlrabi had the highest, and Basil had the lowest; for TEAC, Mustard again had the highest, with Basil having the lowest; finally, for Anthocyanins, Kohlrabi had the highest, and Radish had the lowest. This table can be used as a general reference point if specific secondary metabolites are desired, when making the initial selection of what species to grow for Microgreen production.

Table 3.15: Table of means ± standard error for our six Microgreens species demonstrating the accumulation of the four secondary metabolites studied in this experiment.

Species	Phenolics	Anthocyanins	Flavonoids	TEAC
Basil	2469.69 ± 275.31	2.64 ± 0.49	0.16 ± 0.01	3.32 ± 0.35
Cilantro	1829.2 ± 81.12	2.57 ± 0.52	0.27 ± 0.01	6.07 ± 0.19
Kale	2457.8 ± 209.95	3.23 ± 0.34	0.6 ± 0.02	11.06 ± 0.5
Kohlrabi	3454.02 ± 301.24	13.17 ± 0.66	0.54 ± 0.01	9.07 ± 0.41
Mustard	5358.43 ± 309.08	5.08 ± 0.49	0.54 ± 0.02	20.21 ± 0.92
Radish	2623.22 ± 166.74	1.91 ± 0.14	0.51 ± 0.02	8.23 ± 0.46

3.2.2 Mustard

Because of the overall highly significant effect of Species for all four secondary metabolites measured (Table 3.14), we unnested the Species effect and conducted analyses for each of our Microgreens species. Table 3.16 demonstrates the significant relationships derived from our ANOVA for Mustard Microgreens. For Phenolics, only Light Recipe was significantly associated ($p < 0.01$). For Flavonoids, Seeding Density ($p = 0.04$) and Light Recipe by Fertilizer ($p = 0.03$) were significant. For TEAC, only Light Recipe by Fertilizer was significant at the highest order ($p = 0.02$). For Anthocyanins, we saw no significant associations with our tested effects. Overall, this table shows that there were particular interactions for each of our four secondary metabolites as a result of either the direct effect, or the interaction, of Light Recipe, Fertilizer, and Seeding Density for Mustard Microgreens.

Table 3.16: ANOVA results for Mustard Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent/gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Mustard Effects	Phenolics	Flavonoids	Trolox equivalent	Anthocyanins
	P-Value	P-Value	antioxidant capacity P-Value	P-Value
Light Recipe	< 0.01	0.09	< 0.01	0.12
Fertilizer	0.60	0.01	0.13	0.07
Seeding Density	0.39	0.04	0.80	0.07
Light Recipe:Fertilizer	0.32	0.03	0.02	0.89
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.94	0.61	0.34	0.21
Light Recipe:Seeding Density	0.99	0.28	0.76	0.43
Light Recipe:Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.87	0.27	0.82	0.10

Figure 3.3 demonstrates in greater detail some of the significant differences, and overview of relationships, of the secondary metabolites as a function of Fertilization, Light Recipe, and Seeding Density. Each row of panels is for a particular secondary metabolite, with each sub-panel figure showing Fertilization:Seeding Density. As Table 3.16 shows, for Phenolics, Light Recipe was the only significant effect, and we can see that the High Far Red Light Recipe was significantly greater than all other light recipes. It was on average about 50% greater than all other light recipes. For Anthocyanins, there was no consistent significant difference in effects. For Flavonoids, Figure 3.3 demonstrates that accumulation depended on the type of light and whether or not fertilization occurred. When Mustard was fertilized, for instance, we saw that Far Red light had a significantly lower Flavonoid content compared to other Light Recipes. Interestingly, the TEAC results show that in opposition to Phenolics, the Far Red Light Recipe was significantly lower than all other light recipes, demonstrating an inherent tradeoff. The same inverted effect was seen for the 24VHELED lights, which had lower Phenolics, but higher TEAC when fertilized. This accumulation of TEAC was impacted by fertilization, however, and is not simply the result of light recipe.

Figure 3.3: Accumulation of four secondary metabolites (top to bottom: TEAC, Flavonoids, Anthocyanins, and Phenolics), one for each row, in Mustard Microgreens as a function of fertilization (No, Yes) and Seeding Density (Standard, High). Light Recipes are on the x-axis and are colored as 24VHELED (yellow), High Blue and Green (green), High Far Red (brown), High Red (red), and No Green (purple). Letters above each light recipe are a compact letter display derived from Tukey's HSD ($p < 0.05$) showing significant differences.

3.2.3 Kohlrabi

Table 3.17 demonstrates the ANOVA results for our Kohlrabi Microgreens in controlled conditions. For Phenolics, we saw a significant higher order interaction for the Light Recipe by Fertilization effect ($p = 0.01$). For Flavonoids, we saw a significant higher order three-way interaction for Light Recipe by Fertilizer by Seeding Density ($p = 0.02$), indicating that this was the most highly sensitive secondary metabolite as its accumulation varied by the specific combination of factors. For TEAC, only Light Recipe was significantly associated with its accumulation. For Anthocyanins, we saw that both single-order Light Recipe and Fertilizer effects were significant ($p = 0.01$ and 0.05 , respectively). Given the vibrant red coloring of the Kohlrabi Microgreens, it is not surprising to see the increased accumulation of Anthocyanins compared to other species, as well as it being sensitive to different light types and fertilization. It is also worth noting that Seeding Density was not significantly associated with secondary metabolite accumulation by itself, or as an interaction except for Flavonoids, indicating a lack of sensitivity to competition by Kohlrabi at the level of our seeding densities.

Table 3.17: ANOVA results for Kohlrabi Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent/gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Kohlrabi Effects	Phenolics	Flavonoids	Trolox equivalent	Anthocyanins
	P-Value	P-Value	antioxidant capacity P-Value	P-Value
Light Recipe	< 0.01	0.01	< 0.01	0.01
Fertilizer	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.60	0.05
Seeding Density	0.68	0.36	0.31	0.55
Light Recipe:Fertilizer	0.01	0.02	0.11	0.96
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.64	0.82	0.24	0.44
Light Recipe:Seeding Density	0.71	0.70	0.94	0.41
Light Recipe:Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.83	0.02	0.71	0.92

Figure 3.4 highlights in greater detail the influence and interaction between Light Recipe, Fertilization, and Seeding Density factors for Phenolics, Anthocyanins, Flavonoids, and TEAC in Kohlrabi Microgreens. For Phenolics, High Far Red was once again significantly greater than most other light recipes. However, the degree of accumulation was greatly influenced by fertilization, with the High Far Red Light Recipe having much greater accumulation when fertilized. For Anthocyanins, there was a general pattern where the type of light impacted accumulation; that is, the low intensity 24VHELED had significantly less Anthocyanins compared to all other light recipes. Interestingly, having no Fertilizer increased Anthocyanin content, while having fertilization decreased it. For Flavonoids, there was a clear interaction between Light Recipe and Fertilization, where no single light recipe was best. Similar to Anthocyanin, the Flavonoid contents were lowered by fertilization application. For TEAC, as was the case with Mustard, we saw the same inverted pattern whereby the High Far Red Light Recipe had the most Phenolics, but had the lowest TEAC, which was significant for all combinations of treatments compared to the other light recipes.

Figure 3.4: Accumulation of four secondary metabolites (top to bottom: TEAC, Flavonoids, Anthocyanins, and Phenolics), one for each row, in Kohlrabi Microgreens as a function of fertilization (No, Yes) and Seeding Density (Standard, High). Light Recipes are on the x-axis and are colored as 24VHELED (yellow), High Blue and Green (green), High Far Red (brown), High Red (red), and No Green (purple). Letters above each light recipe are a compact letter display derived from Tukey’s HSD ($p < 0.05$) showing significant differences.

3.2.4 Radish

Table 3.18 details the ANOVA results for Radish Microgreens. For Phenolics, once again only Light Recipe was significantly associated with Phenolics accumulation ($p < 0.01$). However, it is worth pointing out that the Light Recipe by Fertilizer interaction effect was nearly significant ($p = 0.06$), as fertilization increased Phenolic content in all recipes except High Red and 24VHELED. For Flavonoids, there was a significant higher order interaction between Light Recipe and Fertilizer ($p = 0.01$); this was the same highest order interactive effect as both Kohlrabi and Mustard Microgreens as well, indicating a potential cross-species pattern of similar responses to various combinations of light and fertilization. For TEAC, only Light Recipe was significant ($p < 0.01$). For Anthocyanins, only Seeding Density was significant, with the High Density having overall more Anthocyanins, regardless of fertilization or light recipe. This is likely the result of pigment changes due to the high degree of competition at this seeding density intensity; this is especially so given that the Radish was the largest Microgreen we grew and was therefore the most crowded.

Table 3.18: ANOVA results for Radish Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent /gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Radish Effects	Phenolics P-Value	Flavonoids P-Value	Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity P-Value	Anthocyanins P-Value
Light Recipe	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.07
Fertilizer	0.11	< 0.01	0.19	0.53
Seeding Density	0.48	0.52	0.48	0.05
Light Recipe:Fertilizer	0.06	0.01	0.18	0.32
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.77	0.14	0.54	0.19
Light Recipe:Seeding Density	0.74	0.41	0.50	0.40
Light Recipe:Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.87	0.14	0.34	0.50

Figure 3.5 demonstrates in greater detail the detailed layers of interactions across the three treatments in our experiments. For Phenolics, as was the case for both Kohlrabi and Mustard, the High Far Red light recipe had the significantly highest accumulation from most other light recipes. Anthocyanins had a nearly significant ($p = 0.07$) influence of Light Recipe on accumulation, where the low-intensity 24VHELEDs had the generally lowest, and the High Far Red had the highest; as the ANOVA table shows (Table 3.18), the High Density was overall greater than Low Density, independent of fertilization or light recipe as well. For Flavonoids, there was no consistent advantage of any one light recipe, but the High Red recipe with fertilization had the greatest accumulation. For TEAC, the same pattern was observed where the High Far Red Light Recipe had the significantly lowest accumulation values independent of other factors. Interestingly the low-intensity LEDs and the High Red Recipes had the highest overall values.

Figure 3.5: Accumulation of four secondary metabolites (top to bottom: TEAC, Flavonoids, Anthocyanins, and Phenolics), one for each row, in Radish Microgreens as a function of fertilization (No, Yes) and Seeding Density (Standard, High). Light Recipes are on the x-axis and are colored as 24VHELED (yellow), High Blue and Green (green), High Far Red (brown), High Red (red), and No Green (purple). Letters above each light recipe are a compact letter display derived from Tukey’s HSD ($p < 0.05$) showing significant differences.

3.2.5 Kale

Table 3.19 demonstrates the results of our ANOVA for Kale Microgreens. For Phenolics, there were no significant effects for Kale Microgreens. For Flavonoids, we saw a significant third-order interaction for Light Recipe by Fertilizer by Seeding Density, indicating its sensitivity to these different factors ($p = 0.01$). For TEAC, there were also no significant effects. The same lack of significance was seen for Anthocyanins as well. Overall, Kale had the highest average Flavonoid content compared to all other Microgreens species; it is therefore interesting to highlight that this high degree of accumulation was the result of the interacting factors of Light Recipe, Fertilization, and Seeding Density.

Table 3.19: ANOVA results for Kale Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent /gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Kale Effects	Phenolics P-Value	Flavonoids P-Value	Trolox equivalent	Anthocyanins P-Value
			antioxidant capacity P-Value	
Light Recipe	0.31	0.02	0.26	0.32
Fertilizer	0.34	0.01	0.43	0.21
Seeding Density	0.96	0.43	0.40	0.22
Light Recipe:Fertilizer	0.28	0.36	0.33	0.92
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.78	0.79	0.60	0.92
Light Recipe:Seeding Density	0.77	0.74	0.81	0.36
Light Recipe:Fertilizer:Seeding Density	1.00	0.01	0.70	0.69

Figure 3.6 shows in greater detail some of the interactions of our factors on Kale Microgreen secondary metabolite accumulation. For instance, for Phenolics, we found that overall the High Blue and Green Light Recipe was on average greater than the other light recipes, but it also had enough variation that it was not significantly different. For Anthocyanins, the High Blue Green was also greater, and fertilizer also was associated with more accumulation on average, which is the opposite relationship as what was seen for the other three species. Kale Flavonoid accumulation showed a negative effect of fertilizer, but this was modified by both seeding density and fertilization. For TEAC, we saw a general lack of response across the treatments except for a negative response by the High Red recipe when it was fertilized compared to the other light recipes.

Figure 3.6: Accumulation of four secondary metabolites (top to bottom: TEAC, Flavonoids, Anthocyanins, and Phenolics), one for each row, in Kale Microgreens as a function of fertilization (No, Yes) and Seeding Density (Standard, High). Light Recipes are on the x-axis and are colored as 24VHELED (yellow), High Blue and Green (green), High Far Red (brown), High Red (red), and No Green (purple). Letters above each light recipe are a compact letter display derived from Tukey’s HSD ($p < 0.05$) showing significant differences.

3.2.6 Basil and Coriander

For Basil and Coriander, we began our analysis with a grouped ANOVA to observe if there were significant differences between species. As a whole, Table 3.20 shows that there were significant differences for species for three of our secondary metabolites: Phenolics, Flavonoids, and TEAC (0.02, < 0.001, < 0.001, respectively), while Anthocyanins were once again less responsive (p=0.93). Fertilizer was also significant for Phenolics (p = 0.02), while for Flavonoids the interaction between Fertilizer and Seeding Density was significant (p = 0.04).

Because of the significance of the Species effect, we separated further analyses by species. Table 3.21 shows the ANOVA results for Coriander Microgreens for our four selected secondary metabolites. We found there was very little response of Coriander to fertilization or seeding density. However, the Flavonoid content was nearly significant (p = 0.08) for the interaction between fertilizer and seeding density. The same was seen for Anthocyanins and fertilization (p = 0.08).

For our Basil Microgreens, our ANOVA results in Table 3.22 showed that they were much more sensitive to our fertilization and seeding density treatments than Coriander. More specifically, Basil Microgreens were very sensitive to Fertilizer application for both Phenolics (p < 0.001) and TEAC (p < 0.01). No other significant effects were observed.

Figures 3.7-3.10 show in more detail the nested factor differences for our experimental design for all four secondary metabolites. For those species and secondary metabolites that had significant effects, we have shown them using compact letter display, derived from Tukey’s HSD (p < 0.05). For Basil, we can see that overall fertilizer had a negative effect on the accumulation of Phenolics and TEAC. For Coriander, few impacts were seen. However, at the species level, we can see that once again, Coriander had the lowest Phenolic values, but had the highest TEAC values compared to Basil, indicating the consistent tradeoff between them.

Table 3.20: ANOVA results for Coriander and Basil Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent /gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

All Effects	Phenolics P-Value	Flavonoids P-Value	Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity P-Value	Anthocyanins P-Value
Species	0.02	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.93
Fertilizer	0.02	0.57	0.18	0.18
Seeding Density	0.46	0.25	0.22	0.69
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.72	0.04	0.28	0.78

Table 3.21: ANOVA results for Coriander Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent /gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Coriander Effects	Phenolics P-Value	Flavonoids P-Value	Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity P-Value	Anthocyanins P-Value
Fertilizer	0.35	0.94	0.12	0.08
Seeding Density	0.76	0.67	0.46	0.85
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.49	0.08	0.27	

Table 3.22: ANOVA results for Basil Microgreen Phenolics (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW), Flavonoids (mg catechin/mL/gFW), Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (mM Trolox equivalent /gFW), and Anthocyanin (mg/L/gFW) content.

Basil Effects	Phenolics P-Value	Flavonoids P-Value	Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity P-Value	Anthocyanins P-Value
Fertilizer	< 0.001	0.32	< 0.01	0.68
Seeding Density	0.15	0.14	0.19	0.77
Fertilizer:Seeding Density	0.29	0.41	0.38	0.50

Figure 3.7: TEAC content (mM Trolox equivalent/gFW) barplot for Basil and Cilantro Microgreens in Danish pilot study site for controlled experiments. Letters are compact letter displays showing significant differences.

Figure 3.8: Anthocyanin content (mg/L/gFW) barplot for Basil and Cilantro Microgreens in Danish pilot study site for controlled experiments.

Figure 3.9: Flavonoid content (mg catechin/mL/gFW) barplot for Basil and Cilantro Microgreens in Danish pilot study site for controlled experiments.

Figure 3.10: Phenolic content (mg Gallic acid equivalent/L/gFW) barplot for Basil and Cilantro Microgreens in Danish pilot study site for controlled experiments. Letters are a compact letter display showing significant differences.

3.3 RESULTS IN GREECE

The final proof-of-concept experiments were conducted with the small-leaf and mammoth basil cultivars for 3 weeks in total. Each week a portion of the plants was harvested. Half of the samples were tested with NCK and the other half was sent to the Agricultural University of Athens to be measured for their total phenolic content and anti-oxidant activity. The standard methods used were Folin–Ciocalteu, DPPH, and ABTS assays.

In more details:

(a) Folin–Ciocalteu Assay: To determine the content of total phenolic components, a sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) (Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany) solution, 20% w/v, was prepared for the formation of an alkaline environment during the reaction of the sample with Folin–Ciocalteu reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). Then, 1.5 mL H_2O , a 25 μL sample, and 125 μL Folin–Ciocalteu reagent were mixed, and after 3 min, 375 μL of Na_2CO_3 and 475 μL of deionized water were added. After 2 h of incubation in the dark, measurement of absorbance at 725 nm in the ultraviolet spectrometer (visible UV-Vis) (Model V-1200, VWRM Spectrophotometers) followed. All samples were measured three times. The results are expressed in Gallic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) equivalents, for which a standard curve was constructed.

(b) DPPH Assay: The DPPH assay was performed as previously described in [36]. In detail, ethanolic extracts were tested for antioxidant activity with the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH•) radical assay. The DPPH radical (DPPH•) (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) solution (60 μM) was prepared in ethanol. Then, 3.0 mL of the DPPH• solution was mixed with 30 μL of the prepared extract. The solution was then mixed and incubated at room temperature in the dark for 1 h; then, absorbance at 515 nm was recorded. A calibration curve was obtained by using the Trolox (Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) standard ethanolic solution, and the results were expressed in terms of the Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC) as mg Trolox equivalents per mL. All assays were carried out in triplicates.

(c) ABTS Assay: The DPPH assay was performed as previously described in [36]. In detail, the 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonate) radical cation ($\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$) solution was prepared by the reaction of 7 mM $\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$ (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and 2.45 mM potassium persulphate (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) after incubation at room temperature in the dark for 12–16 h. The ($\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$) solution was thus diluted with ethanol to obtain an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.020 at 734 nm. After the extension of 3.0 mL of diluted ($\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$) solution ($A_{734 \text{ nm}} = 0.700 \pm 0.020$) to 30 μL of ethanolic extracts, the absorbance reading at 30 °C, $t = 6$ min after initial mixing (A sample) was acquired. A calibration curve was obtained using the Trolox (Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) standard ethanolic solution, and the results were expressed in terms of Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC) as mg Trolox equivalents per mL. All determinations were carried out in triplicates.

(d) NCK Protocol: 1mg of plants was mashed in 5 ml of 70%ethanol-30% Di water mixture. The plant extract was placed in an Eppendorf tube through a syringe with a PTFE 400nm pore filter attached to its nozzle. The measurement protocol was kept as simple as possible and included: (i) obtaining a baseline in a pure 70%ethanol-30% Di water mixture (30-60 sec), (b) measurement in the plant extract (~1-3min), (c) rinsing in pure ethanol (~1-2 min).

The summarized results from all methods are presented in Table 2.7 and the phase signal measurements obtained from the NCK are showcased in Figure 3.11. Figure 3.12 is a summary of the measurements from all methods, including the analytical techniques and the NCK.

Table 3.23. Results from the Folin–Ciocalteu, DPPH, and ABTS assays in conjunction with the measurements from the immersible photonic sensors.

Basil Type	Week	Folin–Ciocalteu Assay (mg Gallic Acid/g F.W.)	DPPH Assay (mg Trolox/g F.W.)	ABTS Assay (mg Trolox/g F.W.)	Immersible Sensors Phase Change (Rad)
mammoth	1	0.12	0.16	0.35	2.1
	2	1.48	3.92	4.1	1
	3	1.84	2.76	3.93	0.9
small-leaf	1	0.14	0.18	0.39	1.8

	2	2.04	4.02	4.84	1.3
	3	2.12	3.38	4.57	0.7

Figure 3.11: Weekly phase change signals for (a) mammoth and (b) small-leaf basil over a period of 3 weeks (1st week: green line; 2nd week: blue line; 3rd week: magenta line).

Figure 3.12: Total phenolic content expressed in Gallic acid concentration (determined by the Folin–Ciocalteu assay: blue lines, left axis) and antioxidant activity expressed in Trolox concentration (determined by the DPPH and ABTS assays: green lines, left axis; DPPH: open symbols; ABTS: half-solid sym-bols) in conjunction with the NCK signals (phase change) expressed in rads (magenta lines; right axis. The y-axis has been reversed for clarity). Errors bars are set to $\pm 3SD$. Mammoth basil: squares; small-leaf-basil: circles.

To determine the antioxidant activity of mammoth and small-leaf basil varieties, two assays were conducted: the DPPH assay, suitable for lipophilic antioxidants, and the ABTS assay, more suitable for hydrophilic ones. Table 1 indicates that basil samples harvested in week two exhibited higher antioxidant activity in both DPPH and ABTS assays. In the DPPH assay, mammoth and small-leaf samples harvested in week two displayed the highest concentrations of 3.92 mg Trolox/g F.W and 4.1 mg Trolox/g F.W, respectively. Similarly, in the ABTS assay, both basil types harvested in week two demonstrated higher antioxidant activity, with concentrations of 4.02 mg Trolox/g F.W and 4.82 mg Trolox/g F.W for mammoth and small-leaf samples, respectively. Additionally, the Folin–Ciocalteu assay was performed to determine the total phenolic content. Notably, samples harvested in week three exhibited higher content compared to other weeks. Specifically, the mammoth basil sample displayed a concentration of 1.84 mg Gallic acid/g F.W, while the small-leaf basil sample showed 2.12 mg Gallic acid/g F.W. According to these standard measurements, the second week is the optimal time to harvest basil microgreens for maximal nutritional value, as samples showcased higher antioxidant activity and an increase in total phenolic content.

Turning our attention to the NCK results, the phase change signal obtained from the basil extracts notably demonstrates a gradual decrease over the course of the weeks (note that the axis in Figure 3. has been reversed to better illustrate this trend). Interestingly, this downward trend aligns with the findings from the Folin–Ciocalteu assay, hinting at a potential link between the NCK and the total phenolic content of basil microgreens. However, it is important to note that this study was limited in plant variety, and that further investigations are required to validate this hypothesis, as was explained in the recent report by Tran et al. [2] that employed spectral multi-channel spectral sensors as plant reflectance measuring devices to determine the total phenolic content of basil. A more comprehensive exploration would involve a larger set of experiments conducted across multiple generations of hydroponically cultivated crops. Moreover, a more detailed analysis could involve examining the signal gradients and scrutinizing the rate at which the signal approaches a plateau, providing stronger evidence for a potential correlation between the nutrient contents of microgreens and the sensor signals. In addition, it would be useful to determine through other methods the content of chromophore molecules within the various generations of the plants because these could affect the refractive index of the plant extracts. A large-scale experiment performed over several generations of hydroponically cultivated species could enhance the findings of these experiments.

4 CONCLUSION

The activity *T4.2 Experimentation in controlled realistic installations*, had as an objective - *To carry out pilot trials and provide feedback for the refinement and calibration of the GOhydro platform*. In order to fulfill this objective USAMV Cluj built 2 GOhydro platforms, identical, to be able to do experiments in parallel, both in semi-controlled conditions and in operational conditions. The GOhydro platform was built considering the recommendations of *Deliverable 2.1 Multi-modal Sensor Kit Specifications and Requirements*. To achieve semi-controlled conditions, one of the platforms was included in the grow tent Eden Grow XL Growbox Growtent homegrowing 240x120x200 cm. USAMV performed the test with the GOhydro platform in semi-controlled conditions, with 2 species: basil (2 varieties: Germaline Basilic Bio and Basil Grand Vert) and lettuce (3 varieties: Paris White, Little Gem and Lolla Rossa). The methodology used for the research was the one described in the deliverable *D4.1 Trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units*. The growing conditions of the two species of microgreens (basil and lettuce) are specific to semi-controlled conditions, using the Eden Grow plant growing tent. Thus, a temperature was kept in the atmosphere with a maximum oscillation of 3-4 °C, an atmospheric humidity oscillation of 8-10 %, and respectively a constant amount of light (of 1217 $\mu\text{molm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). The irrigation water had a constant temperature of 19-21 °C, a pH of 6.8-7, an electrical conductivity between 1.4-1.5 mS, and respectively a quantity of 6.4-6.5 mg L^{-1} dissolved oxygen. Among the 2 species tested, lettuce ensures distinctly significantly positive Fresh Weight production. By comparison with the Duncan test, it results that the best amount of Fresh Weight is provided by Lettuce - Lolla Rossa, with 889.86 g/m^2 . Basil provides the highest amount of Dry Weight, with a very distinctly significantly positive difference. The variability of the data recorded for total phenols is very high, the statistical processing does not highlight results with a significant difference. Lettuce contains 98-107.33 mg/kg , and basil 141-186.33 mg/kg total phenols. From the morphological analysis of plant development, both in basil and in lettuce, no disease attack is registered, due to the maintenance of the health of the water in the feed basin and a quantity of around 6.4-6.5 mg L^{-1} of dissolved oxygen. An exception is made in the case of lettuce, the Paris White variety, which registers until the end, grade 3 in the degree of attack. This is due exclusively to this variety in which the seed had an inadequate quality for the production of hydroponic microgreens. In conclusion, the experiment in the GOhydro platform, in semi-controlled conditions (plant growth tent) ensures an optimal development of hydroponic microgreens. Very important is the control of vegetation factors, temperature, atmospheric humidity, etc. However, cultivation technology is very important. This resulted in some useful recommendations such as necessity to know / determine the actual germination of the seeds.

Overall, in the Danish controlled environment settings, we have shown the influence of Light Recipe, Seeding Density, and Fertilization—as well as their interactions—on the accumulation of four key secondary metabolites (Anthocyanins, Phenolics, Flavonoids, and Antioxidants) that are valuable for human health. We tested the influence of five different light recipes, two fertilization treatments, and two seeding densities on our Brassicaceae Microgreens; for our two herbaceous Microgreens, Basil and Coriander, we tested two fertilization levels and two seeding density treatments. Overall, we showed that there were significant differences between all six species for all four secondary metabolites. We therefore conducted separate analyses at a higher resolution to better understand some of the nuanced dynamics within each species. We showed that there were unique species-specific responses to the different combinations of experimental treatments.

For instance, some overall patterns we observed were that the High Far Red-Light Recipe generally had significantly higher levels of Phenolics than other light recipes, while at the same time having significantly lower levels of TEAC compared to other light recipes. This tradeoff is important to consider when planning Microgreen production activities. For Phenolics, we found that light recipe was in general the greatest explanatory factor, with High Far Red light components being associated with their production. For Flavonoids, it was the interaction between fertilization and light recipe that generally explained accumulation. We also found that, for Anthocyanins, fertilization generally decreased their accumulation for most species. Furthermore, the lower intensity 24VHELEDs was generally associated with less Anthocyanin accumulation, which is consistent biologically. Concerning TEAC, we showed that Light Recipe was also the strongest explanatory factor; this is not surprising given its inverse relationship to Phenolic content, which also had much of its variation explained by Light Recipe. Overall, in this context, we have shown that most of the light recipes were similar to each other,

except the Far Red recipe, which had specific advantages and disadvantages, and the 24VHELEDs, which were generally associated with lower production of these secondary metabolites, except for TEAC, in which case it performed quite well. Fertilizer overall had different effects on these different secondary metabolites; it had specific nuanced interactions with other factors based on the species examined. The same was seen for Seeding Density as well, which shows the necessity of considering a variety of parameters and their interactions when planning Microgreen production activities.

Overall, we have validated the previous research in Deliverable 2.1 and 1.2 by showing that Microgreens were successfully grown in the identified conditions by controlling specific environmental parameters such as air temperature, relative humidity, nutrient solution, and light incidence. In this Deliverable we have shown how highly controlled environments can be used to perform detailed analyses by varying other experimental factors, such as Fertilization, Seeding Density, or Light Recipe for many different types of Microgreens. In conclusion, we showed that there is much species-specific sensitivity under controlled environmental conditions for secondary metabolite production. Depending on one's desired outputs, such as Phenolics or TEAC, there are inherent biological tradeoffs. We also found that the more expensive, programmable OSRAM lights were generally better, but not always significantly so, compared to the cheaper non-programmable LEDs. Therefore, depending on the desired outputs, the environmental regimes need to be carefully considered and designed in order to maximize productive efforts.

Finally, the experiments conducted at the Greek Pilot Site demonstrated that the concept of using immersible photonic sensors (around which the NCK was built) to assess the nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated plants has shown promising results. The initial experimentation involved testing various microgreen pulps, which established the varying gradient of phase changes between different plant species and within plants of the same species. Building upon this foundation, this study focused on two types of basil microgreens, monitoring them at 1-week intervals over a 3-week period, and comparing the sensor signals with the total phenolic content and antioxidant activity determined by Folin–Ciocalteu, DPPH, and ABTS assays.

The results obtained from the GOhydro NCK hinted at a possible correlation between the detected signals and the total phenolic content of the microgreens. Specifically, it was observed that the signals exhibited a consistent trend that aligned with the changing nutrient composition of the plants. The project's final findings suggest that the immersible photonic sensors have the potential to serve as a tool for assessing the nutrient content of hydroponically grown plants. This represents a promising step toward developing a practical and accessible method for assessing plant nutrient content and that the GOhydro NCK has the potential to become a vital tool in the field of hydroponics.

5 REFERENCES

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